

Beauty in the Songs of Rupkonwar Jyoti Prasad Agrawala: A Discussion

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ABSTRACT

Jyoti Prasad Agrawala is one of the renowned personalities in the world of Assamese culture. He was a bright star of Assamese art and literature. He was a songwriter, composer, playwright, writer and the first Assamese filmmaker. The great Jyoti Prasad Agrawala was born on 17 June, 1903 at Tamulbari Tea Estate in the district of Dibrugarh, Assam. He was born to Paramananda Agrawala and Kiranmoy Agrawala. His ancestors came from outside Assam and settled here. He adopted its language and culture and enriched the vibrant Assamese cultural. Jyoti Prasad also gained practical experience of national liberality and national development in the formation of the Assamese nation from his family. He developed a close relationship with the diverse Assamese culture. His contributions to poetry, drama, essays, criticism, children's literature, etc. were unprecedented. He made his first Assamese film 'Jaymati' He is popularly known as 'Rupkonwar' for his contribution to Assamese culture. Although this great artist passed away on 17 January in the year 1951, he is still living in the blood of every Assamese.

Keywords: Nature, Songs, Green, Romantic, Imagination, Philosophy.

INTRODUCTION

Human life is closely related to nature. Man cannot live without nature. Jyoti Prasad Agrawal was an artist with a huge heart who loved nature. He was a veteran of the 19th century and was a veteran of the 19th century. He painted vivid pictures of nature through his songs. There are also a few songs in Jyoti Prasad's plays that are inseparable from the story. These songs are also worth mentioning that the harp

of the soul of the Assamese is associated with their melodies. Apart from the songs of the plays, his other published songs reflect Jyoti Prasad's own qualities and characteristics. Therefore, the songs he composed have been given a special status by naming them "Jyoti Sangeet". His songs delineates the beauty of nature. The songs are embellished with melody, expression and imagination and are made more attractive by the touch of Assamese folk music. Jyoti Prasad's songs reflect romantic consciousness, love of country life etc. Some of these songs are included in plays, stories, novels, essays, and screenplays, while the rest are independent songs.

Research content and scope:

The topic of our paper is "Beauty in the songs of Jyoti Prasad Agrawala: A Discussion", Only a few of the songs composed by Jyoti Prasad Agrawala will be covered in our discussion paper.

Research Objectives:

The aim of this discussion paper is to bring to light the beauty of nature inherent in the songs of Jyoti Prasad Agrawala, the saint of culture.

Research Methods:

Our discussion paper will generally be conducted in an analytical manner.

Discussion of main topics:

"The worship of beauty is culture or civilization. The total development of culture brings supreme joy to human life. Through culture and civilization, human beings are eager to bring beauty into their lives. In the dark past, the cry that rose — 'towards the light, towards the light' — was itself a declaration of humanity's cultural aspiration, a thirst for light."

“Seuji seuji Seuji O’
 Seuji dharani dhunia!
 Sonowali soichor
 Pothar kolat sobhe
 Rodalire ful-fal
 Senduriya
 Amar sokolor
 Pani di jiyalo
 Maniki modhuri dhan
 Tomaloi aniso
 Jogotore sois
 Era nimati”

(Green, green, beautiful, O green earth, beautiful! The golden fields of rice are adorned with flowers and fruits)

“Seuji seuji Seuji O” is a beautiful song describing the beauty of nature. This song is about the green world. Our crop fields turn golden. The fields also have their own beauty. The flowers and fruits turn orange in the light of the sun. This song is from the play 'Nimati Kaina' by Jyoti Prasad Agrawala. The songwriter seems to have brought the whole world to Nimati. Song literature is an art in which people find the greatness of man. Nature is the most beautiful feeling in human life. The love of life can be found in nature. This song has a lovely message through the description of nature.

Assam is famous for its tea plants. The rows of green tea trees are so beautiful to look at. Our heart enthralled at the eye-catching beauty of tea plantations. Jyoti Prasad Agrawala had a spiritual relationship with the tea plants. He captures the very essence of human experience with sensitivity and authenticity, making his songs impactful. The song “Seujiya Seujiya” highlights the enchanting beauty when he says,

“Seujiya Seujiya
 Lanikoi rule oi
 Gosor sari
 Seuji gosote sonor guti
 Seuji gosote sonor guti lage
 Hira phule mare pohor sati
 Seuji gosote sonor guti.

 Bhati dekhore kuli sowali o,
 Tukurit bhorabi komol pate
 Bhagori jirabi sirisor sate”

The lyricist Jyoti Prasad Agarwala verily understood the relationship between life and nature and its enchanting beauty. There is something about this song that is uniquely charming describing the heart touching sight of the workers rubbing their fingers plucking out the tender, soft leaves from the tea bush.

Similarly, another popular song by Jyoti Prasad Agrawala is “Gose gose pati dile.....”. This particular song is from his renowned play 'Sonit Kunwori'.

“Gose gose pati dile
 Phulore sorai
 Ki ramo ram
 Phulore sorai

 Kolia bhomora
 Gunjari ahe
 Gundhoke dhiyai
 Ki ramo ram

 Oroni tolote
 Parimol renu
 Urowai pabane
 Dile bilai”

This beautiful song mentions green trees. The bees have come to suck the honey from the flowers of the rows of trees and spread the fragrance. The song depicts a true bond between life and nature. There is something about this song that makes it uniquely magical. Therefore, perhaps every Assamese child likes to sing this song along with music education. There is hardly any Assamese artist who has not performed this song once in his lifetime. This song is suitable for the children's minds and with the sweetness of simple words. It gives immense pleasure listening to the song and leaves every child a great joy.

His songs explore a wide reach of human emotions, from joy and love to sorrow and longing. While celebrating beauty and nature, Jyoti Prasad Agarwala's songs also convey tremendous feeling of patriotism. Beauty lies when he uses his music to promote social change and advocates for freedom. He always took pride in Assamese culture and its rich heritage.

The song “Biswabijayee Na-juwan.....” bears a genuine revolutionary spirit in the youth generation. He says,

“Biswabijayee Na-juwan
Biswa bijayi Na-jawan
Saktisali bharatar
Olai aha olai aha
Santan tumi biplobor
.....
.....
Agni bristi ahibo lagise
Gorijise Bajrapat
Silabristi Bhumikampo
Hobo sahasra ulkatat...”

The song is a patriotic anthem, a call to action for the youth population of Assam to rise and fight for the country. The song "Biswabijayee Na-juwan" was sung by Dr. Bhupen Hazarika.

Conclusion:

Jyoti Prasad Agrawala was an extraordinary personality in the field of music. This personality was shaped mainly by his thinking and systematic

approach. The ideal of his life was ‘worship of beauty’. He expected this beautiful position and trust in everyone's heart . He is the artist of the people. His philosophy was based on both his deep faith in scientific modern approaches and his consciousness of Indian heritage. Jyoti Prasad's intellectual being is involved with the imagination of the world citizens. His music is so comprehensive, profound and characteristic that he is living like a heartbeat in every Assamese people. There is a lot of research to be done in the songs of Rupkonwar Jyoti Prasad Agarwala.

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